

1 **Supplementary Figure Legends**

2 **Figure S1. The up-regulation of key members of SCF components in BRCA tissues.** Log2
3 fold change of SCF components identified from the global RNA sequencing. Key factors
4 highlighted include: SKP1 (S-phase kinase-associated protein 1), SKP2, CUL1 (cullin 1),
5 FBXW7 (F-box/WD repeat-containing protein 7), SAG (Sensitive to apoptosis gene), FBXO4
6 (F-box only protein 4) and RBX1 (ring-box 1). The significant actions of SCF components
7 overexpression in breast carcinoma tissues are shown in red.

8

9 **Figure S2. Clinicopathological parameters in paired primary breast carcinoma tissues**
10 **used for qRT-PCR analysis.** To affirm the RNA-seq data, we acquired more primary tissues
11 for the qRT-PCR analysis. Clinicopathological information provided from TMUH, includes
12 diagnosis, histological type, histological grade, pTNM Pathological Classification, stage, ER,
13 PR, HER2, Ki67, age and gender in respective tissue. Paired primary tissues from breast
14 carcinoma (n=32) and corresponding normal breast tissues (n=32) were examined. Tissue
15 samples are categorized into three groups based on cancer staging. (A): 0/IA as initial stage
16 (n=30, including n=15 carcinoma tissues and n=15 corresponding normal breast tissues); (B):
17 IIA/IIB as middle stage (n=18, including n=9 carcinoma tissues and n=9 corresponding normal
18 breast tissues) and (C): IIIA/IIIB/IIIC as late stage (n=16, including n=8 carcinoma tissues and
19 n=8 corresponding normal breast tissues). The mRNA levels (fold change) of FBXL8 are
20 highlighted - red arrow (↑) and blue arrow (↓) indicate upregulation and downregulation,
21 respectively, of the FBXL8 gene expression. F, female; IMC, Invasive mammary carcinoma;
22 IDC, Invasive ductal carcinoma; ILC, Invasive lobular carcinoma; MC, Mucinous carcinoma;
23 MMC, Mixed mucinous carcinoma; DCIS, Ductal carcinoma in situ; fc, fold change; ER,
24 estrogen receptor; PR, progesterone receptor; pN, pathologic lymph node status; pT, Primary
25 Tumour; pM, Distant Metastasis.

26

27 **Figure S3. Clinicopathological parameters in primary BRCA tissues used for IHC**
28 **analysis.** To affirm the transcriptional data, we retrospectively studied primary breast tissues
29 based on the IHC analysis. Clinicopathological information provided from TMUH, include
30 diagnosis, histological type, histological grade, pTNM Pathological Classification, stage, ER,
31 PR, HER2, Ki67, age and gender in respective tissues. A total 60 primary tissues were
32 examined, constituting breast carcinoma (n=30) and paired normal breast tissues (n=30).
33 Samples were categorized into three groups based on cancer staging. (A): IA/IB as initial stage
34 (n=18, including n=9 carcinoma tissues and n=9 normal breast tissues); (B): IIA/IIB as middle
35 stage (n=22, including n=11 carcinoma tissues and n=11 normal breast tissues) and (C): IIIA
36 as late stage (n=20, including n=10 carcinoma tissues and n=10 normal breast tissues). The
37 mRNA levels (fold change) of FBXL8 are highlighted here. Red arrow (↑) and blue arrow (↓)
38 indicate upregulation and downregulation of FBXL8 gene expression, respectively. F, female;

39 IMC, Invasive mammary carcinoma; IDC, Invasive ductal carcinoma; ILC, Invasive lobular
40 carcinoma; MC, Mucinous carcinoma; MMC, Mixed mucinous carcinoma; DCIS, Ductal
41 carcinoma in situ; fc, fold change; ER, estrogen receptor; PR, progesterone receptor; pN,
42 pathologic lymph node status; pT, Primary Tumour; pM, Distant Metastasis.

43

44 **Figure S4. FACS analysis of apoptosis after siRNA transfection treatments of breast**
45 **cancer cells.** Representative histograms of cell apoptosis assay (Annexin V and 7AAD double
46 staining), including controls (PBS and control-siRNA). Two breast cancer cell lines are tested,
47 including MCF7 and MDA-MB231. Early apoptotic cells are indicated by Annexin V⁺/7AAD⁻
48 (shown as %).

49

50 **Figure S5. Representative microscopy images of breast cancer cell invasion.** 24 h after
51 treatment of breast cancer cells with FBXL8 siRNA, control siRNA or PBS control, matrigel
52 invasion assay was performed. FBXL8 siRNA efficiently suppressed breast cancer invasion.
53 Two breast cancer cell lines are tested, including MCF7, and MDA-MB231. After another 24 h
54 incubation, cells that had migrated from the upper to the lower side of the filter were imaged
55 and counted with a light microscope (5 fields/filter). Scale bar is 100 μ m, shown as the red
56 color line (—).

57

58 **Figure S6. Computer modeling prediction of FBXL8-associated proteins.** Several
59 database are used to search the potential proteins associated with FBXL8, including STRING
60 (<https://string-db.org/>), BioGRID (<https://thebiogrid.org/>) and PIPs
61 (<http://www.compbio.dundee.ac.uk/www-pips/>). (A) shows predicted factors by STRING may
62 involve in FBXL8-binding. (B) shows summarized list of FBXL8-binding proteins based on
63 BioGRID and PIPs. (C) shows protein targets either present in any two database or in all three
64 databases, including CUL1, SKP1, CUL2 and CUL7.

65

66

67

68

69

70

71

72

73

74

75

76

77 **Supplementary Figures**

78

79 **Figure S1. The upregulation of key members of SCF components in BRCA tissues**

80

81

Samples Gene	Patient 1		Patient 2		Patient 3		Patient 4		Patient 5	
	Normal	Carcinoma								
83 SKP1	579	594	598	873	473	571	365	269	540	643
84 SKP2	16	35	11	30	11	15	19	21	15	31
85 CUL1	45	72	80	112	75	68	78	96	42	79
86 FBXW7	60	80	61	113	31	41	41	27	55	70
87 SAG	48	81	54	77	43	32	44	68	44	73
88 FBXO4	29	31	35	23	10	22	13	23	26	41
89 RBX1	56	78	49	52	49	37	54	63	50	58

90 Numbers in red indicate increase in expression of the gene (log2 fold change) in BRCA

91 tissues

92

93

94

95

96

97

98

99

100

101

102

103

104

105

106

107

108

109

110

111

112

113

114

115 **Figure S2. Clinicopathological parameters in paired primary breast carcinoma tissues**
 116 **used for qRT-PCR analysis.**

117

118 **A**

Patient	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
Diagnosis	IDC	IDC	ILC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	ILC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	MC	IDC
Histologic type	DCIS	IMC	DCIS	IMC	IMC	IMC	IMC	IMC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IMC	IDC	MC	IDC
Histologic grade	3	3	3	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	3	2	2	1	1
pT	Tis	T1	T1b	T1	T1c	T1a	T1	T1c	T1b	T1c	T1c	T2	T1c	T1b	T1c
pN	N0	N0	N0	N0	N0										
pM	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0										
Stage	0	IA	IA	IA	IA	IA									
ER	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
PR	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-
HER2	3+	2+	3+	2+	2+	3+	3+	2+	1+	2+	2+	1+	1+	1+	2+
Ki67	NA	10%	NA	15%	5%	10%	25%	15%	10%	60%	30%	50%	60%	3%	10%
Age (year)	50	57	48	62	53	68	45	70	41	43	55	50	51	56	50
Gender (F/M)	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
FBXL8 Tumor (fc)	1.9 ↑	0.1 ↓	2.1 ↑	2.2 ↑	1.3 ↑	0.5 ↓	1.5 ↑	1.9 ↑	0.5 ↓	1.8 ↑	<0.01 ↓	0.4 ↓	1.6 ↑	1.5 ↑	1.5 ↑

129

130 **B**

Patient	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
Diagnosis	ILC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC
Histologic type	ILC	IMC	IMC	IMC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IDC	MMC
Histologic grade	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	NA	1
pT	T2	T2	T2	T1c	T2	T1c	T1c	T2	T2
pN	N0	N0	N0	N0	N0	N1	N1	N1	N1a
pM	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0
Stage	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIB	IIB
ER	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+
PR	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+
HER2	1+	1+	0	1+	1+	1+	2+	3+	2+
Ki67	15%	30%	3%	75%	30%	50%	20%	20%	10%
Age (year)	62	49	65	66	54	54	38	72	45
Gender (F/M)	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
FBXL8 Tumor (fc)	1.9 ↑	2.4 ↑	2.4 ↑	<0.01 ↓	3.3 ↑	0.1 ↓	1.1 ↑	1.2 ↑	2.5 ↑

140

141 **C**

Patient	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37
Diagnosis	IDC							
Histologic type	IMC	IDC	IDC	IDC	IMC	IMC	IMC	IMC
Histologic grade	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2
pT	T1c	T3	T2	T1c	T4b	T4b	T2	T2
pN	N2a	N1	N2a	N2a	N2a	N1a	N3a	N3a
pM	M0	M1	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0
Stage	IIIA	IIIA	IIIA	IIIA	IIB	IIB	IIIC	IIIC
ER	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
PR	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
HER2	3+	2+	3+	3+	1+	2+	1+	0
Ki67	35%	80%	50%	40%	30%	30%	20%	10%
Age (year)	44	51	42	50	49	63	56	42
Gender (F/M)	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
FBXL8 Tumor (fc)	1.3 ↑	1.9 ↑	3.4 ↑	1.1 ↑	4.5 ↑	3.1 ↑	1.3 ↑	0.7 ↓

151

152

153 **Figure S3. Clinicopathological parameters in primary BRCA tissues used for IHC**
 154 **analysis.**

156 **A**

Patient	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46
Diagnosis	IDC								
Histologic type	IDC								
Histologic grade	1	2	3	3	1	2	3	3	3
pT	T1c	T1b	T1c						
pN	N0	N1							
pM	M0								
Stage	IA	IB							
ER	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
PR	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
HER2	2+	0	2+	2+	2+	2+	3+	0	2+
Ki67	10%	25%	15%	10%	15%	50%	20%	70%	10%
Age (year)	59	30	46	63	60	71	51	51	58
Gender (F/M)	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F

166 **B**

Patient	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57
Diagnosis	IDC										
Histologic type	IDC										
Histologic grade	2	3	3	3	2	1	2	3	2	2	3
pT	T2	T2	T1c	T2	T2	T1c	T2	T2	T2	T2	T2
pN	N0	N0	N1	N0	N0	N1	N1	N1	N1	N1	N1
pM	M0										
Stage	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIA	IIB	IIB	IIB	IIB	IIB
ER	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
PR	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
HER2	1+	1+	3+	1+	0	1+	2+	0	1+	0	3+
Ki67	25%	40%	40%	50%	75%	5%	10%	40%	5%	5%	50%
Age (year)	60	39	46	56	51	48	66	80	51	51	56
Gender (F/M)	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F

177 **C**

Patient	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67
Diagnosis	IDC									
Histologic type	IDC									
Histologic grade	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	3
pT	T3	T2	T2	T3	T2	T2	T2	T2	T3	T3
pN	N2	N2	N1	N2						
pM	M0									
Stage	IIIA									
ER	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
PR	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
HER2	1+	3+	1+	0	2+	1+	0	0	2+	0
Ki67	50%	65%	40%	60%	8%	20%	70%	30%	50%	30%
Age (year)	42	57	74	50	72	38	72	51	34	70
Gender (F/M)	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F

191 Figure S4. FACS analysis of apoptosis after siRNA transfection treatments of breast
192 cancer cells.

229 Figure S5. Representative microscopy images of breast cancer cell invasion.

230

231

232

233

234

235

236

237

238

239

240

241

242

243

244

245

246

247

248

249

250

251

252

253

254

255

256

257

258

259

260

261

262

263

264

265

266

267 **Figure S6. Computer modeling prediction of FBXL8-associated proteins.**

268

269 **A. STRING**

For FBXL8	Score
SKP1	0.937
CUL1	0.901
ASB2	0.900
UBE2J1	0.900
CUL2	0.900
KLHL13	0.900
CUL7	0.900
CDC27	0.900
LMO7	0.900
RNF130	0.900

270 **C**

282 **B. BioGRID and PIPs**

Database	Predicted targets
BioGRID	SCF E3-associated: SKP1, CUL1, UBE2M. DNA binding protein: ORC4, SNAI1. Others: HSP90AA1, CHMP6.
PIPs	SCF E3-associated: CUL2, PARC, CUL5, CUL1, CUL7, RNF8, RNF31, ANAPC2. DNA binding protein: SMAD1, SMAD2, SMAD3, SMAD4, IRF3, IRF5, IRF8, NBN. Cyclin family: CCNA2, CCNB1, CCNB2, CCND2, CCND3, CCNG1, CCNL1, CCNL2, CCNC, CCNF, CCNI, CCNH, CCNE1, CCNE2, C10orf9, CDKN2B. Others: CNT2.

283

284

285

286

287

288

289

290

291

292

293

294

295

296

297